
Intellectual Property Right in Indian Entrepreneurial Perspective

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Abstract:

This abstract is an overview of the critical role of intellectual property right in the journey of startups, emphasizing their significance as a cornerstone for securing new ideas, fostering creativity, attracting investments and safeguarding competitive advantages. Startups basically born from breaking ideas, different, disrupting innovations making the protection of intellectual property which is a difficult, crucial mission. This protection of intellectual property encompasses a diverse array of assets which includes patents, trademarks, copyrights and trade secrets which are unique in value in giving shape to the IP rights serve as powerful catalysts for funding and growth. Through the judicious application of IP strategies, startups can fortify their position in growing market.

Keywords: *Intellectual Property Rights, Indian copyright, Industrial property, Startups Patents Copyright violation, Hurdles, Solutions.*

What Is Intellectual Property?

Intellectual property rights are the rights given to person for his creation of mind. It is a right of a creator, innovator who creates or innovates something unique or new in any field, area whether it may be literature, computer programming, sculpture., This right is given for certain period. After the completion of this period it will become general.

Two Categories of Intellectual Property:

Intellectual property rights are divided into two categories-

Copyrights And Rights Related To Copyrights:

Author who writes any book or create any literary work including poems, stories, articles, paintings, designs, literary work, dramas are his own property. Nobody can copy it or publish it without his prior permission. This right has been given for certain period. This protection has been

given for the purpose of stimulating the creative work, innovative work will be done.

Objectives of Copyright: The object of copyright is to promote progress along with to encourage authors, composers and artists to create original works. Initially copyright law

applied to only to copying of books. Over time others use solutions as translations and derivative work including maps, music, dramatic works, paintings, motion pictures, architectural drawings, sound recordings, photographs.

General Principles of copyright:

Principle of copies 2) Audio, image & audio visual copies 3) Multimedia products, 4) Archiving 5) Digital libraries 6) Electronic copies 7) Electro copying and networking.

Copyright Violation:

Hacking, Virus attack *Cutting of communication* Cracking * Violation Of

privacy *Data fiddling * Spreading Misinformation* Alteration of information *E mail security destruction.

Industrial Property:

Industrial property can usually be divided into two main areas.

- 1) Trademark –If any company firm has its own logo or any trademark or icon which identify its goods from where it originates from where this is for to ensure and stimulate for competition and to protect customers
- 2) Industrial designs-This property has been protected primarily to stimulate new innovations and the creations of industrial designs and trade secrets.

This protection is given for particular period .Typically for 20 years in case of patents

Startups:

Under the startup India initiative, eligible companies can get recognized as startups by The Department of Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT) through the startup India Initiative has executed various projects and undertaken recurring models to propel *Indian Startup Ecosystem*. For example BHASKAR

Bharat startup knowledge Access Registry, Bhaskar, is envisioned as one top digital platform where diverse startup ecosystem stakeholders can seamlessly connect and collaborate catalyzing the growth and success of the startup ecosystem across India. By providing a comprehensive platform for connection, knowledge sharing and search ability ever increasing amounts of wealth stored in intellectual property flaring up. According to S and P index for the 5 larger companies by market cap.

Intangible intellectual property assets have skyrocketed in total company valuation. Patents provides several advantages for our analysis -

- 1) It is in the interests of innovating firms and actors to get adequate protection

for their IP, we can assume that they apply for the kind of protection corresponding to the nature of the innovation. Because we have no reason to think .Industrial innovation would be registered as a copyright, data about applications would be true to the kind of innovation as in one particular country.

- 2) The world intellectual property organization (WIPO)BASED IN SWITZERLAND IS IN CHARGE OF receiving filings administering the 26 international ip treaties and resolving IP disputes among its 193 member countries
- 3) The rights granted by patent abstentions whatever the kind of patent and whatever the country of origin also referred to in IP rights as the filling office protect for a duration of 2e National Policy of IPR2016,In May 2016, the National Intellectual Property Rights Policy 2016 was approved as a vision statement to direct the country's future IPR growth. creative India; Innovative India is the motto of IPR policy 2016.

The government of India has designated the DEPARTMENT OF industrial policy 7 promotion (DIPP) Ministry of Commerce as the Nodal department to coordinate, direct and Monitor the implementation and future development of IPRs in India.

Certain Issues Related To IPR In India:

Issue of Implementation:

A significant hurdle is getting the judiciary and enforcement officials to address concerns with intellectual property rights.

Conflicts with Overlapping Provisions:

Over protection of intellectual property occurs when different bodies of intellectual property law simultaneously

protect the same topic. It is challenging to balance private property rights in India.

1) **Issue Related to Plagiarism:**

Plagiarism is another serious problem. It is the act of taking another person's intellectual property, which includes words, slogans, designs, confidential information and creative works of authorship and utilizing them as one's own without acknowledging the original author or inventor.

2) **Improper enforcement of Intellectual Property Laws in Cyberspace:**

On the Internet, Intellectual property rights are applicable, but their enforcement is the key concern. Publishers contend that the internet undermines their rights to intellectual property since it fundamentally alters the nature and methods of publishing, leaving their products very susceptible to online piracy.

3) **Decentralized Internet Management:**

Due to internet's management being decentralized, anyone can misuse extensively disseminate work on the electronic network known as Cyberspace through a variety of means. An individual can simply share a piece of art with newsgroups via email or on a personal website. The law governing intellectual property rights has caused issues for those working with advanced technology, such as computer programmers. The law stipulates that something must either be in writing to be protected by copyright or a machine to be protected by a patent.

4) **No equivalent legislation to the Western Copyright Laws:**

Although the Indian Copyright Act followed international norms, Indian Copyright Act has significant shortcomings when compared to Western Copyright Laws. Because India does not join the "WIPO Internet Treaties", there is no equivalent legislation to the US DMCA in India.

5) **Protective Measures for Electronic Data:**

The current Indian Copyright Act makes no mention of "technological protective measures" or the need to preserve electronic rights management data. The Indian Penal Code, 1860 (IPC) contains several sections that could provide legal protection for technological measures. The IPC's Section 23 refers to "Wrongful gain or wrongful loss".

Protecting Traditional Knowledge: Traditional knowledge is like a rich mine, especially in the medical area. Govt. of India is required to safeguard the traditional knowledge by prohibiting MNCs from obtaining patents on traditional culture.

Above all, the government established the Traditional Information Digital Library (TKDL) to stop traditional knowledge from being patented.

Data Exclusivity: According to claims made by foreign investors and MNCs, Indian Law does not protect against the unfair commercial use of test results or other data that is submitted to the government as part of a request for the government to approve a pharmaceutical or agrochemical product for sale

Global Pressure and Compliance: India faces international pressure to conform to global IPR standards, often perceived as beyond its TRIPS agreement obligations. Balancing international expectations with domestic needs and development goals is a continual challenge.

Solutions:

- 1) For addressing IPR related disputes, a suitable resolution process is required.
- 2) India must fix any gaps in its IP Laws and regulations if it is to fully benefit from the transformative advantages of a strong IP system.
- 3) The expansion of the innovation ecosystem with improved IPR

safeguards is necessary for the success of India's flagship programs, Make in India and Startup India.

- 4) To encourage the Indian Industry to innovate as well as to protect and enforce their ideas, there has to be greater knowledge about the development, protection and enforcement of IPRs.

Conclusion:

- 1) Addressing the issues related to intellectual property rights requires a multi-pronged approach, including legal reforms, strengthening enforcement mechanisms, enhancing judicial capacities and fostering culture of innovation and respect IPR.
- 2) Moreover, policies need to be inclusive, considering India's development needs, public health concerns and the imperative to foster innovation and creativity.
- 3) To improve efficiency and reduce the time needed to issue patents, India has implemented several improvements to its IPR framework.
- 4) In the nation, innovation culture is becoming more prominent. India is

in a good position to prioritize R&D. This has resulted in an increased rating in the global innovation index over tixplqaining factors and implications for the Indo-Pacific region

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